

LIGNIN BIO-BASED ADDITIVE FOR STRENGTH AND MOISTURE RESISTANCE IMPROVEMENT OF FIBROUS PACKAGING MATERIAL

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Abstract: *Fibrous packaging materials have recently attracted even more attention, mainly due to new Single-Use Plastic (SUP) directive which announced a ban of six single-use plastic items; plastic grocery bags, straws, stir sticks, plastic cutlery, six-pack rings and food containers made from hard-to-recycle plastics. One of the promising sustainable alternatives is fibrous packaging material but needs to be properly modified to sustain sufficient compression strength and moisture resistance. Using lignin bio-based formulation METNIN™ SHIELD is one of the solutions, since improves strength and moisture resistance of the fibrous packaging material.*

Keywords: lignin, additive, fibrous packaging material, strength and moisture resistance

1 INTRODUCTION

The size of the global packaging market is estimated to USD 915 billion, out of which one third represent plastic (Metsa Board, 2021). Due to plastic pollution (Parker, 2019) and new SUP directive (Digitalpartner.si, 2021) forces us to search for alternatives which have to be rapidly developed and implemented in a safe and efficient manner. Fibrous packaging materials offer a promising sustainable alternative for many applications that currently use plastic-based solutions but need to be properly modified to sustain sufficient compression strength (ISO, 2008) and moisture resistance (ISO, 2014). Lignin is known as potentially valuable renewable raw material for the production of biodegradable and recyclable materials (Calvo Flores and Dobado, 2010),

which is another feature that need to be exploited for these purposes. In MetGen, lignin bio-based formulation METNIN™ SHIELD was developed to achieve above mentioned goals.

In the present work, SCT index and Cobb₆₀ value were used for determination of strength and moisture resistance of coated and uncoated samples made of OCC fibers and different papermaking additives.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

OCC (“old corrugated cardboard”) fibers taken from produced OCC paper from ICP pilot paper machine were used for the first two experiments, while for the third experiment, OCC fibres, supplied by DS Smith were used. First the OCC fibers were disintegrated in a laboratory disintegrator for 30 000 revolutions in order to achieve the complete disintegration of the fibers. Commercial papermaking additives, sizing agent AKD (Melamin), retention aid Percol (Solenis), cationic starch Papiran SKM (Helios), filler CaCO₃ (Calcit), dry strength resin Hercobond 2515 (Solenis), polymers Xelorex 1200 and Xelorex 1300 (Solenis) as well as lignin bio-based formulation METNIN™ SHIELD (MetGen) were added to OCC fibers to prepare 110 gsm or 155 gsm laboratory sheets on Rapid Köthen sheet forming machine. After that, the addition of different additives was evaluated with the SCT index (Short-Span Compression Test) according to ISO 9895:2008 and determination of water absorptiveness according to Cobb method (ISO 535:2014).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the first set of experiments, blank sample (BS) made of OCC fibers, 1,0% sizing agent AKD and 0,01–0,02% retention aid Percol was prepared and the influence of the addition of cationic starch Papiran SKM, filler CaCO₃ and their combination as well as commercial dry strength resin Hercobond 2515 and polymers Xelorex 1200 and Xelorex 1300 was evaluated with the SCT index and Cobb₆₀, which is clearly presented in Figure 1. It is well known, that fillers deteriorate mechanical properties of the paper, but usually 5–35% of fillers are added to the paper, depending on its final use. Paper, made of OCC fibers is often used for the production of linerboard where the addition of the filler is desired, mainly due to lower cost so for the experiment 16,0% of filler was added in the blank sample.

Figure 1: Influence of different additives on SCT index and Cobb₆₀ value

The addition of cationic starch in the blank sample increases the SCT index, reaching the maximum with addition of 2,0% of cationic starch (26,0 Nm/g). On the other hand, the addition of the filler decreases the SCT index, from 23,0 Nm/g to 16,2 Nm/g, which increases again with the addition of cationic starch, but does not exceed the value of the blank sample. SCT index is comparable with the maximum value of the first set of the experiments when 3,0% of commercial polymer Xelorex 1300 and 1,0% of Hercobond is added to the blank sample. Additives, such as cationic starch, filler, dry strength resin and/or polymers do not have much effect on the Cobb₆₀ value. Its value depends on the addition of the sizing agent which is added in the blank sample.

In the second set of experiments, two different laboratory sheets with 40% dryness were prepared; first only from OCC fibers and second with the addition of 16,0% filler CaCO₃ and 0,01% retention aid Percol, on which 6 gsm of lignin bio-based formulation METNIN™ SHIELD was added using spray technique followed by one- or a two-stage drying process. One-stage drying process was performed in the drying section of Rapid Köthen machine at 92 °C for 7 min while the two-stage drying process was performed in the Rapid Köthen followed by final curing in the oven at 105 °C for 60 min. The influence of the filler and drying processes were evaluated with the SCT index and Cobb₆₀ value.

Figure 2: Influence of METNIN lignin and drying process on SCT index and Cobb₆₀ value

Bio-based formulation METNIN™ SHIELD greatly improves the initial values of SCT index and Cobb₆₀ in both cases, using only OCC fibers and with the filler addition. The increasing of SCT index is in both cases approximately 50%. SCT index decreases with the addition of the filler but does not go under the initial value even of the blank sample without 16,0% of filler (23,0 Nm/g). A similar story is with water absorptiveness, where addition of METNIN™ SHIELD decreases water hydrophilicity near to reference value range, while the samples with the filler or one-stage drying regime move values away from reference values. Addition of the filler increases the Cobb₆₀ value from approximately 29,0 gsm up to 45,0 gsm when adding METNIN™ SHIELD and using two-stage drying process and from 33,5 gsm up to 51,5 gsm when using one-stage drying process. If we compare commercial additives and use of lignin bio-based formulation METNIN™ SHIELD on SCT index and Cobb₆₀, we can conclude that using METNIN™ SHIELD give us significantly better results.

In the third set of experiments 155 gsm laboratory sheets with 40% dryness were prepared on Rapid Köthen sheet forming machine using DS Smith OCC fibers on which 4,8 gsm of lignin bio-based formulation METNIN™ SHIELD was added using two-stage drying process. The influence of different relative humidity (50% and 90%) on SCT index and Cobb₆₀ was evaluated, since one of the main tasks of the packaging is protection of the product from external influences (mechanical, biological, chemical, environmental and atmospheric), that also relative humidity represents.

Figure 3: SCT index and Cobb₆₀ value vs relative humidity

Cobb₆₀ value of OCC fibers without the sizing agent is above 200 gsm. With addition of METNIN™ SHIELD formulation, the water absorptiveness decreases, which is shown by lower Cobb₆₀ value (from 200 gsm to 22,5 gsm). This value of the Cobb₆₀ is similar as with the standard addition of commercial sizing agent AKD and is in the range of commercial usual paper products, intended also for coffee cup production. SCT index is increased by 23% when using METNIN™ SHIELD formulation at 50% of relative humidity and by 47% at 90% of relative humidity. SCT index is decreased in both samples (OCC fibers and OCC fibers with METNIN™ SHIELD formulation) when putting the samples from 50% to 90% of relative humidity. The strength value of coated sheet measured at 90% RH corresponds to the strength value of uncoated sheet measured at 50% RH.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Bio-based lignin formulation METNIN™ SHIELD improves moisture resistance of the paper which was shown by low water absorptiveness value. Such value is in the range of commercial sized material used for usual paper products. The results of compression strength showed improvement at 50% and 90% of relative humidity compared to uncoated laboratory sheets. Usual papermaking additives such as starches, dry strength agents and polymers improve compression strength by 15%, while bio-based lignin formulation METNIN™ SHIELD improves compression strength for approximately 50%. Based on the result, we can conclude that METNIN™ SHIELD formulation has shown great potential in the field of fibrous packaging material.

Further research will be focused on different ways of applying the METNIN™ SHIELD formulation on paper, modification and optimization of coating formulations to achieve even better compression strength and moisture resistance of fibrous packaging material. Another challenge will be upscaling the laboratory results on industrial level.

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